

Example #	IPA	gloss	audio reference
(1a)	kursiŋman ^{dr}	slip	NT1-98015B 00:05:53
(1b)	sulpronj	lizard	NT5-200801-2 00:49:27
(2a)	nsfen	something.like.that	NT5-200801-2 00:23:03
(2b)	ntiŋmat	peace	NT1-98015A 00:27:44
(3a)	kfet	dry.tasting	BR1-012-LE 00:02:00
(3b)	fket	spicy	BR1-012-LE 00:02:33
(3c)	tnus	sting	NT1-98015B 00:10:58
(3d)	ntuk	rope	NT1-98015A 00:42:38
(3e)	tlai	warm.oneself	NT1-98015A 00:03:35
(3f)	ltia	weave.end	NT5-200801-1 00:23:32
(3g)	k̄ptaē	divide	NT5-200801-2 00:41:11
(3h)	t̄k̄pak	frizzy	NT5-200801-3 00:09:52
(4a)	kal	dress.oneself	BR1-078 00:51:04
(4b)	ka:l	digging stick	BR1-078 00:35:02
(4c)	puk	to.be.full	BR1-036 01:08:42
(4d)	pu:k	to.cough	BR1-036 01:09:02
(5a)	pes	talk	BR1-057 00:33:58
(5b)	ipes	3S.RS=talk	BR1-057 00:34:05
(5c)	kafopsa	1S.IRS=PSP.IRS-talk-TS-3S.O	NT1-98001A 00:30:21
(5d)	nafsa:n	DET-talk-NMLS	BR1-057 00:45:02
(6a)	nak̄pel	belly	BR1-043 00:30:05
(6b)	nak̄plen	belly-3S.DP	BR1-043 00:30:18
(7a)	naŋal	gum	BR1-043 00:19:07
(7b)	naŋlam	gum-2S.DP	BR1-043 00:19:35
(8a)	kerkerai	be.strong	NT1-98003B 00:12:21
(8b)	kerkrai	be.strong	BR1-011 00:00:09
(9a)	n ^{dr} rakat	lift.up	NT5-200801-2 00:20:29
(9b)	n ^{dr} rkat	lift.up	BR1-078 00:13:16
(10a)	naŋmo:l	body	BR1-057 00:21:27
(10b)	naŋmo:lin	body-3S.DP	BR1-057 00:21:45
(11a)	naŋmel	tail.of.fish	NT1-98015A 18:33:00
(11b)	naŋmlen	tail.of.fish-3S.DP	NT1-005A 18:33:00
(12a)	to:l	pass	NT1-98014A 00:19:08
(12b)	to:li	pass-TS-3S.O	NT1-98014A 00:19:06
(13a)	itil	3S.RS=say	NT1-004B 00:15:18
(13b)	itli	3S.RS=say-TS-3S.O	NT1-004B 00:33:05
(14a)	isu:r	3S.RS=gouge	NT1-20003B 00:11:54
(14b)	isu:ra	3S.RS=gouge-TS-3S.O	NT1-20003B 00:12:44
(15a)	itūk̄p	3S.RS=shoot	NT1-98002A 00:06:43
(15b)	it̄k̄pa	3S.RS=shoot-TS-3S.O	NT1-98017B 00:44:52
(16)	itili	3S.RS=say-TS-3S.O	NT1-004B 00:12:09
(17a)	natko:n	village	NT1-005A 00:06:57
(17b)	natoko:n	village	NT1-004B 00:08:58
(17c)	natoko:n	village	NT5-StringBand-001 00:12:36
(18a)	te:sa iskei	child one	NT1-98010A 00:33:17
(18b)	tša nmatu	child female	NT1-98009A 00:10:51
(19a)	tesa nanwei	child male	NT1-98003B 00:24:18
(19b)	tša nanwei	child male	NT1-98003B 00:23:51
(20a)	kepnuti	3S.IRS=close-TS-3S.O	NT1-98009A 00:29:20

(20b)	rulfeka	3P.RS=around-TS-3S.O	NT1-98009A 00:37:12
(20c)	rutkali	3P.RS=touch-TS-3S.O	NT1-98010A 00:07:05
(21a)	kumol	sweet.potato	NT1-98015A 00:11:56
(21b)	rakum	crab	NT5-200801-2 00:34:18
(21c)	n ^d rokos	follow	NT5-200801-2 00:21:51
(22a)	popo:t	white.crab.sp	NT5-200801-2 00:34:18
(22b)	tete	some	NT5-200801-3 00:05:57
(22c)	sasu	fish.sp.grouper	NT5-200801-2 00:44:00
(23)	asoso	1S.RS=call-TS-3S.O	NT1-004A 00:27:21
(24a)	ra ^k pas	2D.RS=pick.flower	BR1-068 00:25:00
(24b)	r ^k pek	wrapped.laplap	BR1-014 00:14:08
(25a)	kalek	1S.IRS=look	NT1-20001B 00:17:24
(25b)	klet	shellfish.sp	BR1-014 00:34:01
(26a)	k ^p ale:r	2S.IRS=return	NT1-98009B 00:02:11
(26b)	k ^p laŋ	open	NT1-98015A 00:24:47
(27a)	tamarin	tamarind	BR1-068 00:24:04
(27b)	namru:n	something	NT5-200801-2 00:03:00
(28a)	petoŋ	petanque	NT1-98010A 00:39:37
(28b)	pton	coral sp.	NT5-200801-2 00:35:16
(29a)	afoka	avocado	NT5-200801-1 00:00:31
(29b)	nafkal	battle	NT1-98003-A 00:18:09
(30a)	maloput	middle	BR1-068 00:24:04
(30b)	talpuk	crowd	NT1-98001B 00:12:28
(31a)	memelim	shellfish sp.	NT1-98015B 00:01:42
(31b)	namlas	bush	NT5-200801-2 00:02:55
(32a)	tarisal	flotsam	BR1-063 00:28:48
(32b)	k ^p arsor	fish sp.	NT5-200801-2 00:37:55
(33a)	timen	arrow	NT1-98017A 00:15:01
(33b)	tmen	father	NT1-004B 00:12:22
(34a)	nalaŋ	song	BR1-057 00:11:02
(34b)	nlaŋ	wind	NT1-98004A 00:13:52
(35a)	pako	shark	NT1-98004A 00:19:43
(35b)	pko	be.interested	NT5-200801-2 00:39:47

NT1: Thieberger, Nick. 1995. South Efate (Vanuatu) (NT1), Digital collection managed by PARADISEC. Open access.

<http://catalog.paradisec.org.au/collections/NT1>.

NT5: Thieberger, Nick. 2000. South Efate (Vanuatu) (NT5), Digital collection managed by PARADISEC. Open access.

<http://catalog.paradisec.org.au/collections/NT5>.

BR1: Billington, Rosey. 2017. Rosey Billington Nafsan materials (BR1), Digital collection managed by PARADISEC. Open access.

<http://catalog.paradisec.org.au/collections/BR1>.